

The Unjournal

Evaluation Summary and Metrics: "Global potential for natural regeneration in deforested tropical regions"

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ABSTRACT

We organized two evaluations of the paper: "Global potential for natural regeneration in deforested tropical regions"^[1]. From the evaluators' joint synthesis report "Williams et al. (2024) aim to identify the magnitude and spatial distribution of biophysical potential for natural forest regeneration... Methodological concerns fundamentally challenge the validity and utility of the central 215 Mha estimate of regeneration potential." Key concerns include "data leakage from contemporaneous predictors," "confounding by socioeconomic factors and predictor choice" and "discrepancy in estimated magnitude and lack of historical validation". Both evaluators suggest specific remedies; E2 also provides code for a bootstrap-based confusion matrix. These evaluations are linked below; the [synthesis report](#) is at the bottom of this document.

Evaluations

1. [Evaluator 1](#)
2. [Evaluator 2](#) (Cannon Cloud)

([Synthesis report](#))

Overall ratings¹

We asked evaluators to provide overall assessments as well as ratings for a range of specific criteria.

I. Overall assessment (See footnote²)

II. Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5): On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' should this be published in?³ *Note: 0= lowest/none, 5= highest/best.*

	Overall assessment (0-100)	Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5)
Evaluator 1	50	3.5
Evaluator 2 (Cloud)	50	4.5

See "[Metrics](#)" below for a more detailed breakdown of the evaluators' ratings across several categories. To see these ratings in the context of all Unjournal ratings, with some analysis, see our [data presentation here](#).⁴

See [here](#) for the current full evaluator guidelines, including further explanation of the requested ratings.

Note:

Evaluation summaries

Anonymous evaluator 1

Strengths

- Proposes an empirically novel approach to answer highly policy-relevant questions
- Provides a sound overall methodology which is tractable and replicable

Critiques

- Trained model does not enable prediction into the future given currently observed conditions
- Predictions do not represent pure biophysical potential despite being framed as such
- Regrowth longevity is not addressed
- Policy targeting implications qualified by additionality and opportunity costs

Evaluator 2 (Cannon Cloud)

This paper aims to model and predict the global potential for natural regeneration in deforested tropical regions for 2016 and 2030, respectively, using a machine learning random forest (RF) approach. The study’s aim and methods are novel and important, given the potential benefits of natural regeneration on carbon sequestration (amongst many other ecological and environmental outcomes) and the lack of pan-tropical analysis. The paper’s current estimates are the first we have for understanding the scope of natural regeneration as an effective climate change mitigation measure.

However, my review identifies several significant conceptual and methodological concerns that fundamentally affect the validity and interpretability of the results and predictions, particularly concerning the paper's goal of informing restoration prioritization.

Metrics

Ratings⁵

[See here](#) for details on the categories below, and the guidance given to evaluators.

The ratings provided by Cannon Cloud reflect revised ratings following a consultation with Evaluator 1 (Anonymous). The previous ratings are included as a footnote beside Cloud’s new ratings for reference.

	Evaluator 1			Evaluator 2		
	Anonymous			Cannon Cloud		

Rating category	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Comments	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Comments
Overall assessment ⁶	50	(40, 60)		50	(40, 60) ⁷	8
Claims, strength, characterization of evidence ⁹	20	(15, 25)	10	5	(0, 10) ¹¹	12
Advancing knowledge and practice ¹³	60	(50, 70)	14	70	(50, 90) ¹⁵	16
Methods: Justification, reasonableness, validity, robustness ¹⁷	20	(15, 25)	18	5	(0, 10) ¹⁹	20
Logic & communication 21	50	(41, 60)	22	40	(30, 50) ²³	24
Open, collaborative, replicable ²⁵	95	(90, 100)	26	30	(15, 45) ²⁷	28
Real-world relevance 29 , 30	90	(80, 100)	31	80	(60, 100) ³²	33
Relevance to global priorities ³⁴ , 35	90	(80, 100)		80	(60, 100) ³⁶	

Journal ranking tiers

[See here](#) for more details on these tiers.

	Evaluator 1 Anonymous			Evaluator 2 Cannon Cloud		
Judgment	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI	Comments	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI	Comments
On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' <i>should</i> this be published in?	3.5	(3.0, 4.0)		4.5	(3.5, 5.0)	
What 'quality journal' do you expect this work <i>will</i> be published in?	5.0	(5.0, 5.0)	37	5.0	(5.0, 5.0)	38
See here for more details on these tiers.	<i>We summarize these as:</i>					
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.0: Marginally respectable/Little to no value • 1.0: OK/Somewhat valuable • 2.0: Marginal B-journal/Decent field journal • 3.0: Top B-journal/Strong field journal • 4.0: Marginal A-Journal/Top field journal • 5.0: A-journal/Top journal 					

Claim identification and assessment (summary)

For the full discussions, see the corresponding sections in each linked evaluation.

	Main research claim ^{39}	Belief in claim ^{40}	Suggested robustness checks ^{41}	Important 'implication', policy, credibility ^{42}

Evaluator 1 Anonymous	Biophysical conditions can support natural regeneration in tropical forests over 215 million hectares globally. Five countries account for 52% of this estimated potential.	I have low confidence in the estimated 215 Mha being an accurate figure on biophysical potential. It is likely a lower bound to the true value, due to anthropogenic factors.	To formulate the prediction as a prediction of future outcomes conditional on currently observed covariates.	The results imply information about the spatial distribution of low-cost forest restoration opportunities.
Evaluator 2 Cannon Cloud	"We estimate that an area of 215 million hectares... has potential for natural forest regeneration..." ... "above-ground carbon sequestration potential of 23.4 Gt C (range, 21.1–25.7 Gt) over 30 years."	My belief in the accuracy of the headline claim – 215 Mha of potential natural regeneration – is low.	The first minor point in the referee reports suggests using multiple kinds of machine learning algorithms, for at least some regions, to compare sensitivity.	That there exists a vast, globally significant area where cost-effective natural regeneration could be prioritized to meet climate and biodiversity goals.

Evaluation manager's discussion/Process notes

Why we chose this paper

From the notes we shared with the evaluators:

This paper looks at using machine learning to predict areas of forest that are regrowing naturally. This is important from a policy perspective: it is the UN decade of restoration; restoring forests is seen as key to meeting climate obligations; many countries have reforestation targets (eg Bolivia for 1m ha of forest regrowth). Understanding where and how much might happen naturally seems crucial, and in that sense, this paper offers compelling insights. For this very reason, it is important to be sure that the conclusions obtained are sound and robustly capture the actual relationships without biasing factors and data leakage.

Evaluation process

We sought evaluators with demonstrated expertise in

- the application of machine learning to economics and policy; issues like data leakage and causal inference, and
- tropical forest ecology and restoration, climate change mitigation and carbon sequestration.

We suggested the evaluators may wish to specifically consider the following issues:

Although this paper was published in Nature, we would like to get independent feedback on a few aspects of it, particularly:

- Is there any “leakage” in the ML implementation (i.e. using features that are related to the target and would not be available in real-world use)?
- Inference: They are suggesting that the areas that should be prioritised are those with a high predicted ability of regrowth – is this correct? Do they make a clear and strong case for this?
- Additionality (i.e. the extent to which an intervention leads to outcomes that would not have occurred in its absence).
- *What robustness checks/alternative specifications would you like to see?*
- Have they chosen the most appropriate statistical learning approach (random forests)?

We also checked that these issues had not been fully addressed by the authors’ responses to the peer review reports in Nature, which (commendably) have been [publicly shared](#).

After the evaluators returned their initial reports, we checked these carefully, both from our own understanding and using AI reasoning models, particularly considering and querying whether the issues raised by the evaluator had already been addressed in the paper or its appendices, or in the responses to the Nature peer review reports. We shared these responses with the evaluators, giving them the opportunity to adjust.

We next consulted the authors, who declined to formally respond to these evaluations. They suggested that “Many of the points raised by the reviewers are addressed by reading the paper and its supplementary material in more detail. In particular, the recommendations made by reviewer 2 would likely be regarded as unpractical by experts who work with remote sensing derived forest data.” We checked these carefully again, querying reasoning models and verifying their responses, and sharing these with the evaluators. The consensus was that most of the points were still relevant and were not addressed in the supplementary material, nor in the responses to the Nature reviews. Most (but not all) of the recommendations were deemed fairly practicable.

As always, if they authors wish to respond in the future, we will share their responses here.

Because of the paper's prominence, we encouraged the evaluators to share and discuss their reports with each other and seek consensus. After extensive back-and-forth, they prepared the report below.

Evaluators’ synthesis report⁴³

Introduction

Williams et al. (2024) [1] aim to identify the magnitude and spatial distribution of the biophysical potential for natural forest regeneration (assuming socioeconomic factors are mitigated). After discussing and re-evaluating the study, the evaluators agree on significant methodological and interpretative issues. Methodological

concerns fundamentally challenge the validity and utility of the central 215 Mha estimate of regeneration potential.

Primary Concerns

1. Data Leakage from Contemporaneous Predictors:

The model induces data leakage due to predictors that are contemporaneous with the outcome. Net primary production, burned area, road density, and soil characteristics were recorded over the same time period as the outcome, and these predictors incorporate information that is influenced by regeneration itself. When predicting into the future, information about these predictors is not available. As a result, the reported model accuracy overstates true predictive performance. For a more detailed discussion, see Evaluator 2's report, section "[1. Data Leakage Concerns](#)".

2. Confounding by Socioeconomic Factors and Predictor Choice:

A considerable methodological challenge in identifying biophysical regrowth potential arises from how socioeconomic constraints moderate and are correlated with natural regeneration.

The trained model has learned from the entire domain of historical regrowth and non-regrowth areas. Regrowth historically happened only where *both* biophysical factors and socioeconomic conditions were favorable. As the model does not explicitly incorporate socioeconomic conditions, it will tend to predict more regrowth when an area has biophysical factors that tend to correlate with socioeconomic conditions that favor regrowth. Thus, contrary to what the authors argue, dropping socioeconomic predictors *diminishes* the model's ability to identify biophysical potential in isolation. Furthermore, retained biophysical predictors such as 'distance to forest' and local forest density are partially anthropogenically determined. In sum, the proposed method cannot support the interpretation of the estimates as 'purely biophysical potential for natural forest regrowth'.

3. Discrepancy in Estimated Magnitude and Lack of Historical Validation:

Because the model, as argued above, effectively estimates a combined biophysical and socioeconomic potential due to highly correlated predictors, its aggregate prediction should conceptually align with the historical total observed under similar mixed influences. However, the authors' estimate of 215 Mha of expected natural regeneration is strikingly larger than the benchmark from the training data by Fagan et al. (2022) [2] of 31.6 Mha \pm 11.9 Mha (for 2000-2016), even when accounting for increases in land availability due to deforestation or uncaptured historical socioeconomic constraints. Williams et al. (2024) do not report their own model's prediction for the 2000-2016 historical period (a "hindcast"), a crucial missing validation against this benchmark.

Other Issues

Our review synthesis identified an additional important issue – the lack of transparency in how model accuracy was assessed, which in turn undermines the ability to evaluate the 215 Mha estimate:

(i) The confusion matrix in Table A1.2 appears to validate the model by comparing its predictions for 2030 against the Fagan et al. (2022) regrowth data for 2000-2016. However, the 215 Mha estimate is derived from a prediction based on forest cover, forest density, and distance to forest updated to reflect conditions in 2015 and 2018. This raises the concern that validating a model designed to predict future potential against past outcomes is not a true test of its predictive power for the future.

(ii) Table A1.2 reports 92% user's accuracy for the 215 Mha of predicted regrowth, which implies at least ~197.8 Mha of regrowth in ground truth and even more when considering omission error. The authors do not provide any explicit detail about the size or nature of the reference data and how it relates to the much smaller observed regrowth (~5.4 Mha) in the training dataset.

Several other points raised in the individual evaluator reports further undermine confidence in the conceptual basis, spatial distribution, and overall magnitude of the estimates. These concerns, detailed in the evaluator reports, include:

- **Policy Implications, Additionality, and the Nature of "Biophysical Potential":** Specific nuances in the policy implications drawn by Williams et al. (2024) are problematic. This includes issues concerning additionality, opportunity costs, and claims of "low intervention effort," all of which are complicated by the unclear nature of the "potential" being mapped. The core problem is the lack of distinction between regrowth that would occur under a business-as-usual scenario and the "potential" that assumes socioeconomic constraints are overcome.
- **Uncertainty Estimation:** The overly narrow confidence intervals reported for some estimates may not fully reflect the uncertainties introduced by the modeling choices and potential biases.
- **Ephemerality of Forest Regrowth:** Concerns remain regarding how the short-term persistence of forest regrowth (often less than four years, as noted by Evaluator 1) is accounted for in estimates of long-term potential and carbon sequestration.

IV. Conclusion

Due to the fundamental methodological issues outlined, the central findings of Williams et al. (2024) are challenging to interpret and reconcile with the underlying data. The evaluators recommend that further inquiry into the topic address these issues where possible and carefully consider how any unresolved limitations affect the interpretation of results. This is essential to improving the scientific understanding and evidence base that guide policy decisions.

References

1. Williams, B. A., Beyer, H. L., Fagan, M. E., Chazdon, R. L., Schmoeller, M., Sprengle-Hyppolite, S., Griscom, B. W., Watson, J. E. M., Tedesco, A. M., Gonzalez-Roglich, M., Daldegan, G. A., Bodin, B., Celentano, D., Wilson, S. J., Rhodes, J. R., Alexandre, N. S., Kim, D.-H., Bastos, D., & Crouzeilles, R. (2024). Global potential for natural regeneration in deforested tropical regions. *Nature*, 636, 131–137. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-08106-4>

Footnotes

1. *Note (3 Jun 2025): The evaluators have not yet revised their individual ratings after their mutual conversation, although at least one of them intends to do so. We will update this when they do.* [↵](#)
2. We asked them to rank this paper “heuristically” as a percentile “relative to all serious research in the same area that you have encountered in the last three years.” We requested they “consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.” [↵](#)
3. See ranking tiers discussed [here](#). [↵](#)
4. Note: if you are reading this before, or soon after this has been publicly released, the ratings from this paper may not yet have been incorporated into that data presentation. [↵](#)
5. *Note (3 Jun 2025): The evaluators have not yet revised their individual ratings after their mutual conversation, although at least one of them intends to do so. We will update this when they do.* [↵](#)
6. Judge the quality of the research heuristically. Consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.

[↵](#)

7. Original rating: (30, 50, 80) [↵](#)
8. This rating reflects the paper's high potential and novelty tempered by severe methodological flaws that likely invalidate its main quantitative estimate (potential area) and compromise its predictive reliability. The midpoint below 50% reflects the current lack of credibility in the headline results. The wide CI reflects that the paper could be rated very poorly if the flaws are deemed insurmountable or very highly if major revisions successfully address the core issues, given the importance of the topic. [↵](#)
9. “Do the authors do a good job of (i) stating their main questions and claims, (ii) providing strong evidence and powerful approaches to inform these, and (iii) correctly characterizing the nature of their evidence?”

This was on the newer form only [↵](#)

10. The research questions are clearly identified and novel. The execution has a number of shortcomings which render the reliability of the results highly questionable. Results are incorrectly framed as pure biophysical potential. [↵](#)

11. Original rating: (20, 40, 60) [↵](#)

12. The paper clearly states its important questions and claims regarding natural regeneration potential. While the machine learning approach applied is novel and potentially powerful, the evidence provided for the main quantitative estimate (215 Mha) is significantly undermined by major methodological concerns, particularly the failure to correct for substantial omission errors in the input data and potential data leakage issues. Furthermore, the authors do not fully characterize the impact of these limitations on their results. This combination of clear goals but flawed evidence and characterization justifies a below-average midpoint rating (40%), while the wide credible interval (20-60%) reflects the tension between the paper's novelty and importance versus the current lack of credibility in its core findings, which could potentially be addressed through major revisions. [↵](#)

13.

To what extent does the project contribute to the field or to practice, particularly in ways that are directly or indirectly relevant to global priorities and impactful interventions?

[↵](#)

14. Disregarding methodological critique, the study asks relevant research questions and provides a conceptually novel approach to answer them. As such, future research should build on the study and address the methodological shortcomings. [↵](#)

15. Original rating: (40, 50, 90) [↵](#)

16. This rating reflects the paper's high relevance to critical global priorities like climate change and biodiversity loss, and its potential to inform impactful interventions through cost-effective natural regeneration. The novel global approach represents a potentially significant contribution. However, the current contribution to practice is severely limited by major methodological concerns outlined in this review, particularly those affecting the reliability of the headline quantitative estimates and the map's utility for prioritization. These flaws substantially reduce the paper's current impact compared to its potential, justifying a midpoint rating. The wide credible interval acknowledges that successful major revisions addressing the core methodological issues could elevate the paper's contribution considerably. [↵](#)

17. Are methods clearly justified and explained? Are methods and their underlying assumptions reasonable? Are the results likely to be robust to changes in the assumptions? Have the authors avoided bias and

questionable research practices? [↵](#)

18. The overall methodology is well motivated and appropriate. However, shortcomings in implementation render the reliability of the results highly questionable. [↵](#)

19. Original rating: (10, 30, 50) [↵](#)

20.

Adjusted rating comment: 'I would point out though this is just a simple mistake and overall they were pretty close, though this nuance doesn't show up in the rankings'.

This rating reflects a significant disconnect between the clarity of the methods' explanation and their appropriateness and robustness in practice. While the Random Forest approach is standard and described adequately, its application suffers from serious issues, including potential data leakage and, critically, the use of input data with known, large omission errors that are not corrected for in the final estimate. This leads to results that are likely biased, not robust to underlying assumptions, and presented without adequate characterization of the substantial uncertainty inherited from input data errors. These methodological shortcomings significantly undermine the credibility of the paper's main quantitative findings, justifying a low midpoint rating, although the wide credible interval acknowledges the potential for improvement if these fundamental issues were rigorously addressed. [↵](#)

21. Are concepts clearly defined? Is the reasoning transparent? Are conclusions consistent with the evidence (or formal proofs) presented? Are the data and/or analysis, including tables and figures, relevant to the argument? [↵](#)

22. The method and its outputs are clearly defined. The conclusions and discussion are much more opaque and lack concrete policy prescriptions. [↵](#)

23. Original rating: (50, 65, 80) [↵](#)

24. This rating primarily assesses the clarity and internal consistency of the paper's presentation. The authors clearly define their core concepts and transparently explain their analytical reasoning and workflow. The conclusions drawn, such as the 215 Mha potential area, are consistent with the direct outputs of the specific modeling approach presented, and the supporting data, figures, and tables are relevant to the argument. However, the paper could more accurately characterize the nature of its evidence alongside its main claims by giving greater prominence to the known limitations of the input data (particularly omission errors) and their potential impact on the results' interpretation, rather than primarily discussing these in the methods or supplementary information. Despite this weakness in fully contextualizing the evidence, the overall clarity and transparency warrant an above-average rating for this specific criterion. [↵](#)

25.

Would another researcher be able to replicate the analysis? Are the method and its details explained sufficiently? Is the source of the data clear? Is the data made as widely available as possible, with clear labeling and explanation? Do the authors provide resources that are likely to enable future research and meta-analysis?

└

26. All data sources are referenced, publicly available, and the method is described in detail. └

27. Original rating: (15, 30, 45) └

28. The authors clearly explain their methodology and cite the sources for their input predictor variables. Furthermore, they make their final output maps (potential for regeneration) publicly available via Zenodo. However, direct replication of the analysis is severely hampered by the lack of publicly available code (available only upon request), and the absence of the derived training and validation dataset (the millions of points labeled as regeneration/non-regeneration). While the methods description is detailed, the inability for another researcher to easily access the exact code and training data to verify or build upon the modeling workflow significantly limits reproducibility and falls short. Therefore, despite the value of the output data, the overall support for replication and future analysis is rated below average. └

29.

Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic and relevant to practitioners?

└

30.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" └

31. Disregarding methodological critique and the resulting caveats, the topic and results are highly relevant for policymakers and practitioners. └

32. Original rating: (50, 60, 70) └

33. The authors clearly define concepts as used in their study and transparently describe their analytical workflow. The main conclusions drawn, including the headline potential area estimate, are logically consistent with the evidence generated by their specific modeling approach, and the supporting data, figures, and tables are relevant and well-utilized (though sometimes missing). [↵](#)

34. Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions? [↵](#)

35.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" [↵](#)

36. Original rating: (50, 60, 70) [↵](#)

37. The study is already published in a top journal. Impact potential and novelty clearly warrant this ranking, but methodological shortcomings and thin implications from the results do not carry that far. Methodologically better and more informative work is published in lower tier journals. [↵](#)

38. I think this should be published in Nature if they can work through my main critiques. But if there is still some confusion about natural regrowth vs tree-planting, for example, or difficulty modeling uncertainty due to omission error, I would suggest this be moved down slightly in journal quality. [↵](#)

39.

The evaluator was given the following instructions:

Identify the most important and impactful factual claim this research makes – e.g., a binary claim or a point estimate or prediction.

Please state the authors' claim precisely and quantitatively. Identify the source of the claim (i.e., cite the paper), and briefly mention the evidence underlying this. We encourage you to explain why you believe this claim is important, either here, or in the text of your report. [↵](#)

40. Evaluators were asked: To what extent do you *believe* the claim you stated above? Feel free to express this either a. in terms of the probability of the claim being true, b. as a credible interval for the parameter being estimated, or c. however you feel comfortable. [↵](#)

41.

We asked:

[Optional] What additional information, evidence, replication, or robustness check would make you substantially more (or less) confident in this claim?

Feel free to refer to the main body of your evaluation here; you don't need to repeat yourself. Please specify how you would perform this robustness check (etc.) as precisely as you are willing. E.g., if you suggest a particular estimation command in a statistical package, this could be very helpful for future robustness replication work. [↔](#)

42.

We asked:

[Optional] Identify the important *implication* of the above claim for funding and policy choices? To what extent do you *believe* this implication? How should it inform policy choices?

Note: this 'implication' could be suggested by the evaluation manager in some cases. As an example of an 'implication' ... in a global health context, the 'main claim' might suggest that a vitamin supplement intervention, if scaled up, would save lives at a \$XXXX per life saved.

We did not ask this in the 'applied stream' as it is most likely redundant.

[↔](#)

43.

See the above discussion of how we came to the evaluators' synthesis.

3 Jun 2025: The evaluation managers have added some stylistic edits that were approved by one but not both of the evaluators; we aim to revisit this. [↔](#)

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1. Williams, Brooke A, Hawthorne L Beyer, Matthew E Fagan, Robin L Chazdon, Marina Schmoeller, Starry Sprenkle-Hyppolite, Bronson W Griscom, et al. 2024. 'Global Potential for Natural Regeneration in Deforested Tropical Regions'. *Nature*, 1–7. [↔](#)
2. Fagan, M. E., Kim, D.-H., Settle, W., Ferry, L., Drew, J., Carlson, H., ... others. (2022). The expansion of tree plantations across tropical biomes. *Nature Sustainability*, 5(8), 681–688. [↔](#)